

***music as an invitation* - comments on experiences of
online participatory concerts
(a small handbook)**

THIS IS A DRAFT version (the final version, with minor corrections and multimedia illustrations, will be publicly available on Research Catalogue in July 2025)

Késia Decoté Rodrigues
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INTRODUCTION

For the past few years, the practice of sharing concerts through the internet has been growing considerably. From YouTube premieres to Instagram Lives and platforms dedicated to streaming the programme of major concert halls, individual musicians and big institutions have been exploring ways to share music in the digital domain.

This increase of interest about online concerts was particularly experienced between 2020 and 2021, during the COVID-19. With the restrictions to social gatherings to contain the spread of the coronavirus, and many concert halls and other music performance venues being closed, many performers (including myself) turned their attention to the possibility of presenting their music performance through the internet.

Besides being an alternative for that particular moment, we could notice some positive possibilities offered by digital concerts. For example, they can reach further audiences, and they allow multimedia explorations.

However, online concerts can also affect negatively one of the essences of the live music experience: the relationship between performer(s) and audience.

In my own experience in the online concerts that I gave during that time, I could not help missing a feeling of connection - although I knew that my spectators were there 'at the other side of the screen' and we would even interact via chat, I could not *feel* that we were together.

I asked myself:

- 'what can we do to bring up a feeling of being together when we are experiencing a concert remotely?'

Then, reflecting on how to address this question, I carried on asking:

- 'if we invite the audience to participate in the creation of an online concert, how would the participatory proposal make an impact on the experience of music through the internet?'
- would the interpersonal relations and affective aspect from the participatory process help us to feel more connected, when watching 'our' concert remotely?

From those questions, my postdoctoral research project was born: *music as an invitation - liveness in digital piano performances through participating audiences*¹ <https://musicasaninvitation.com/>.

In this 2-year practice-based research project, I invited participants to join me in online workshops to create an online concert collaboratively.

For the first year of project, the invitation was aimed exclusively to adult participants who self-identified as women. I then had a group of 14 women from 7 countries, who met monthly through video-conferences, for around 7 months. The participants themselves decided how they wanted to develop the creative process, and how they wanted to present the final result of this collaboration. The online concert resultant of this process was a collage of the material produced by the participants throughout the project. This collaborative concert received the title ***music as an invitation (year 1: 2023-2024)***, and it was presented as a YouTube premiere on the 6th April 2024. <https://youtu.be/-zCYo5FRr8I?si=RShXkmE4o7WADIWE>

In the second year of project, the invitation was focused to teenage girls age 13 to 17 year old. I had a group of 6 girls from 4 countries. The participatory process with these girls lasted for approximately 4 months, when we had the aim to realise a piece of music that composer Alwynne Pritchard wrote specifically for this project. The participants had some specific tasks to

¹ *Music as an invitation* was as a practice-based postdoctoral research with duration of 2 years. It was based at the Grieg Academy, University of Bergen, being funded by the European Union.

be done for this piece, which involved them to write creative texts, interact with each other materials, explore sounds of objects of their everyday lives, and record short videos. Thereafter, the material produced by the participants integrated a piece for video and piano called ***Hecate writes***, which was performed in a live streamed concert which had the title ***rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*** and happened on the 28th March 2025 at the Grieg Academy, in Bergen, Norway. https://www.youtube.com/live/QxYgccd5DZ0?si=1RVDCmil2_XK9G8k

This short handbook will share the learnings from these participatory concerts which were developed as part of the *music as an invitation* project.

Using those two concerts as case studies, I will attempt to briefly present the basic steps on putting together participatory online concerts. I will also discuss some relevant points to be observed during those steps, drawing specifically from my experience in the *music as an invitation* project.

The aim of this book is primarily to offer insights for the production of artistic works: online concerts. Therefore, I have tried to trim out jargon and elements that are more pertinent to academic contexts. However, since the experiences narrated here came from online concerts which were part of a research project, sometimes some academic tone may emerge, incidentally.

As it is reasonably common in practice-based projects, the roles of artist and research leader were blended in the music as an invitation project. Also, in participatory works, sometimes the roles of artist and facilitator are combined. Taking this in consideration, here in this book I used those terms interchangeably. Although this blending of the roles of artist, project leader, and facilitator may not be appropriate for some projects, here it expresses the context of my activities in the *music as an invitation* project.

Regarding the 'participatory' focus of this book, it is fairly understandable that, any performance, intrinsically, involves audience participation. As Gareth White highlights, 'without participation performance would be nothing but action happening in the presence of other people'.²

Indeed, for a work to be a work of art - be it a piece of music, a theatre play or a painting, for example - the listener / spectator / viewer must actively make sense of it in their minds:

'... works of art aren't received like a package sent from heaven; rather, you only get raw material and need to complete the work of art within yourself'.³

However, in this book we will focus on concerts where the audience is tangibly involved in the music making process. In that sense, the criteria for audience participation, here, includes creative contribution to the realisation of the music content and/or to the production of the concert.

'Participatory performance is defined here as a form where the audience is able to affect material changes in the work in a way that goes beyond the inherent interactivity in all live performance'.⁴

Also, here I differentiate between participatory and interactive works. For the purposes of this book, I am seeing 'interaction' as the proposal to do some kinds of exchange with the art work⁵,

² WHITE, G.. (2013). Audience Participation in Theatre: Aesthetics of the Invitation (p. 3). (Function). Kindle Edition.

³ TRÖNDLE, M. (Ed.). (2020). Classical Concert Studies: A Companion to Contemporary Research and Performance (E. Dorset, Trans.; 1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003013839>

⁴ BREEL A. (2015). Audience agency in participatory performance: a methodology for examining aesthetic experience. *Participations*, 12, p. 369.

⁵ ALMENBERG, Gustaf. (2010). Notes on Participatory Art : Toward a Manifesto Differentiating It from Open Work, Interactive Art and Relational Art. Central Milton Keynes: AuthorHouse.

while 'participation' relates to 'involving the audience in the creative process, transforming them into active participants'.⁶

While works that fit more into the 'interactive' category also can be seen as involving audience participation, in this book I will focus on proposals which offer the audience a greater degree of active engagement, indeed creatively contributing to the work⁷ - be it a piece of music or the online concert as a whole.

It is relevant to note that the experiences which provide the basis for this book were indeed small scale in terms of number of participants. Also, they involved the use of reasonably affordable infrastructure and technological knowledge on the level of an average internet user.

This considered, this book has no intention to be comprehensive, neither as a timeless guide. Rather, this volume can be seen as a glimpse into situated experiences on putting together participatory online concerts. And this is a topic which, by its very nature, is in rapid and constant evolution.

My aim is that this volume can contribute to other curious and adventurous artists and producers who are interested in exploring creative ways to share music with their audiences. Here, we are experimenting with the possibilities offered by the digital domain, challenging its limitations by involving people in the action of making music even though remotely, and, ultimately, thriving to do what music does best: bring people together.

⁶ <https://avantarte.com/glossary/participatory-art>

⁷ BREEL A. (2015). Audience agency in participatory performance: a methodology for examining aesthetic experience. *Participations*, 12, p. 369.

Chapter 1: First steps - the idea, motivations and goals

1. Identify the original spark

Similarly to the historical 'eureka' story, sometimes, a new idea for a project comes to us in an instant of surprise, like a revelation. However, despite its spontaneous appearance, those sparkle-moments are usually the tip of the iceberg: the culmination of an process of reflection and synthesis which is undergoing in our minds even when we are not completely aware of it.

Other times, we see idea emerging through a consciously laborious process of researching, analysing, and writing countless drafts.

Either way, it can be helpful to identify where the idea for the project came from. For example, during the development of the *music as an invitation* project, multiple questions emerged competing for attention and making the path unclear. On those moments, it was helpful to go back to the origins of the ideas and set the project back to course.

2. Set a topic, theme, or a central element

After the initial spark, it can be helpful to frame that initial idea into a topic or a theme, or to set an element around which the project will be developed. This theme, topic, or central element, will work as guideline for the activities to be done during the project. It is possible, however, that those items are intentionally left to be chosen by the participants. In this case, we can say that the participation itself is the central element of the project.

3. Map the field

Now, a wise step is to do some research in order to identify what has been already done related to the project idea. These can be practical or theoretical works. By identifying related works, it is possible to draw some inspiration, to learn from previous experiences, and to identify which new insights the new project can bring.

4. Are there objectives?

Sometimes, setting the general objectives of the project - i.e., having a clear vision of where you want your project to go to - can help significantly in the step of choosing the methods to apply in the development of the project. However, other times an exploratory approach is preferred, with the decision of 'seeing where it goes'.

Either way, it can be interesting to have it clear which path will be taken, and communicate it to the participants at the beginning of the project (including the goals, if this is the chosen approach).

Specifically about the choice for a participatory proposal, it is advisable that the motivations for this choice are clear in the project design, as well as what it is wanted to be achieved with the audience participation. Having the goals for the audience participation clear can be helpful to understand about which participatory category¹ the project fits in, and to decide which methods and/or participatory strategies are going to be used in the development of the project.

Case study: the *music as an invitation* project

For some years I have been interested in exploring creative ways to share music with my audiences. During my PhD, I had started investigating different ways to set up the space of the performance, then experimented different ideas for the performer-spectator relationship, ([hyperlink to 'Les jours' - https://vimeo.com/167755164](https://vimeo.com/167755164)), and eventually explored new ways (within the classical piano tradition) to engage my own body as a expressive element in my piano performances ([hyperlink to 'myths & visions' - https://vimeo.com/244712499](https://vimeo.com/244712499)).

¹ Categories of Participation, according to Kaija Kaitavuori, include: Target, User, Material, and Co-creator. KAITAVUORI, Kaija. 2020. *The Participant in Contemporary Art : Art and Social Relationships*. London: I. B. Tauris & Company, Limited.

In that journey, I became more and more interested in inviting my audience to take a more active role in the live music experience. In some of my projects I had already started to explore some kind of audience participation, for example: inviting the listener to choose which pieces they wanted to have in the programme ([hyperlink to 'My piano in the midst of the turmoil' - https://vimeo.com/232814993](https://vimeo.com/232814993)), or proposing specific walks in moments during a performance ([hyperlink to 'myths & visions' - https://vimeo.com/244712499](https://vimeo.com/244712499)).

I wanted then to explore in depth the topic of audience participation within a practice-based research context.

Then, suddenly, the world was hit by the coronavirus pandemic, and social distancing was reinforced to prevent the spread of the virus. With music venues closed, many musicians (including myself) have turned to the digital domain as a way to keep connected with their audiences during that time of restrictions.

As mentioned previously in this book, I did some online performances during the coronavirus lockdowns. Those included a series of improvisations delivered by WhatsApp calls, some Instagram Lives, and a YouTube Premiere.

Although those were really valuable experiences, I also felt some compromise on my relationship with my listeners: although we were connected, I could not feel the 'liveness' of the shared music experience. Although my audience was just there, at the other side of the screen, I still felt as if we were not *together*.

Then, **the initial spark** for the *music as an invitation* project emerged: audience participation as a way to make us feel more connected to each other when experiencing music through the internet!

The central idea of the project would be then to investigate if the audience participation would contribute to build a sense of *liveness* (what means, the feeling of being part, of always being connected to other people²) in the experience of an online concert.

In order to '**map the field**' of what had been done before regarding this idea, I consciously recalled my own experience as a performer and audience member in online concerts. I also looked for literature about online participatory projects. Finally, since this was a research project, I studied texts about *liveness* in online performances to ground my reflections about the central idea.

Although I could find abundant examples of online concerts, and of participatory music projects, for the combination of online *and* participatory I complemented my literature review with publications from the area of theatre, which has a longer tradition in non-conventional practices regarding the conventions of spectatorship.

In the *music as an invitation* project, the **general objective** was then to create a collaborative online concert. This objective brought the project into the 'co-creator' category, where the participants 'bring their own initiatives and ideas into play and to contribute to the content of the work'.³

The **specific objective** was related then to the research context of this project, where I aimed to examine how the participatory proposal would make an impact on the audience's experience of the music digitally and remotely.

² AUSLANDER, P. (2008) "Live and Technologically Mediated Performance", The Cambridge Companion to Performance Studies, T.C. Davis, ed., Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. p. 111

³ KAITAVUORI, Kaija. 2020. The Participator in Contemporary Art : Art and Social Relationships. London: I. B. Tauris & Company, Limited. p. 70

From the specific objective, it became clear that the collection of audience feedback was a crucial element in the methodology.

However, in the second phase of the project, there was the need to adjust the general objective, in order to fit the characteristics of the group of participants. The general objective now was redirected to realise a piece of music. This piece of music was commissioned by the project to the composer Alwynne Pritchard, and included collaborative elements designed specifically to that group of participants. This redirection of the general objective brought the second phase of the project to the boundaries between 'co-creator' and 'material' categories where, in the latter, 'people participate to perform a set task, and the form and content of their contribution is defined in advance and controlled by the artist'.⁴

The redirection of the general objective in the second phase of the research implicated a change of methodology as well. However, the specific objective remained the same than the project's original proposal, including collection of audience feedback as a key element of the research aspect of the project.

⁴ KAITAVUORI, Kaija. 2020. *The Participator in Contemporary Art : Art and Social Relationships*. London: I. B. Tauris & Company, Limited. p. 52

Chapter 2: Who is your audience?

When designing a participatory online concert, we may wish to define our target audience. To this, an array of factors can be considered, such as: age group, gender, level of experience with music (and/or with a specific style of music), language, location, access to technology, specific set of skills, experience in a specific area of knowledge, among others.

The set of a target audience will work hand in hand with the strategies for recruitment. For example, a call for participants in English may, by itself, filter recruitment to English speakers primarily.

Also, the place where the call or invitation will be placed, could be tailored according to age group as well. For example, some social media platforms are more seen by one age group than another. Also, posting calls for participants in places such as schools or cultural centres may, by itself, channel the recruitment to specific groups which may be distinguished by age, location, gender, areas of interest or social backgrounds.

Additionally, the technology required to participate in the project can also be an element that will determine the group to be recruited. For example, in the *music as an invitation* project, the initial idea was to run the online workshops via the platform Zoom. However, one of the potential participants could only participate using her mobile phone, since she did not have a computer, neither access to wireless connection at home. Considering that it could become complicated for her to download a new software using her mobile data, I decided to do the workshops through Google Meet instead, which was a platform which she had used before in her mobile phone and was more familiar with.

Naturally, these factors and other factors may be taken in account besides the content and visuals of the advert.

After the recruitment, a possible step is the selection of participants among the ones who have responded to the call/invitation. The selection can take place for a number of reasons, including: capacity, required skills / knowledge, confirmation of eligibility of the prospective participant according to the criteria of the project, among others.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

The project *music as an invitation* had a gender aspect in its proposal, therefore the call to participants was directed to adult women (first year of the project) and girls age 13 - 17 years old (second year of the project).

One of the first learnings in the recruitment process of the first year of this project, was regarding the definition of gender. After sending out the first version of the poster with the call for participants, I have received the questions:

‘Are you including anyone identifying as a woman (i.e. also trans women) in your call for women participants? What about non-binary people?’

Therefore, for this project, the call for participants was updated with the note: ‘all self-identified women are welcome’. ([Illustration: Call for participants](#))

The posts were in English and in Portuguese, which also framed the target audience.

The recruitment was done through posts on social media channels, which included my Instagram and Facebook pages, as well as my host university’s. The recruitment was also forwarded by other musicians and music promoters which were part of my network.

This decision ended up mostly attracting participants which were already in contact with the my work. This factor incidentally created a group already inclined to engage in an intimate creative process, which was indeed a positive aspect for the proposal of the project.

The recruitment did not ask for any further selection, since it naturally ended up with 14 active participants - which was within the expected group size.

Case study 2: piece *Hecate writes* & concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

The recruitment of participants for the second year of the *music as an invitation* project focused on groups of teenage girls from Norway, Brazil, and the UK. The decision for such a age was part of the agenda of the project regarding gender inequality and empowerment of voices traditionally neglected in the field of classical music. Since this project could have included some postings on social media, the specification of the minimum age, 13 years old, took in consideration the requirement for access to some of the most popular social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. On the other hand, the maximum age, 17 years old, tried to ensure that all the participants were approximately in the same phase of adolescence.

The language of the recruitment was English and Portuguese, which naturally filtered the call to participants who could speak either of these languages.

The recruitment was firstly made by sending emails to school and private piano teachers, also to NGOs and social programmes dedicated to development of girls. In this process, different contact persons asked for different (and sometimes contradictory) adjustments to the invitation text and additional materials such as:

- broader texts with more details about the activities involved in the project
- a more succinct text with just a general call
- a poster with attractive visuals and less text
- a poster with more textual information about the project

On one hand, these adjustments shows the need for the tailoring of the recruitment to each context. On the other hand, it might have given a hint about the most appropriate strategy for each project, since the contacts who asked for more modifications in the call / invitation ended not being very productive in attracting participants anyway.

In the meantime, calls on social media were also posted, which did not bring much results either. [\(Illustration: Call for Participants - EVEVEVE\)](#)

For this phase of the *music as an invitation* project, the most effective recruitment came through contacts with friends and individual invitations to their teenage daughters. The adjustment of the recruitment strategy coincided with the change of the method. Now, instead of developing a whole concert with the participants, it was decided to focus on the development of the music which had been commissioned for the project - *Hecate writes*, by Alwynne Pritchard. The delimitation of the location was also amended, now including France as well.

In this process of inviting potential participants individually, I would firstly get in contact with the parents explaining the project and asking if they would like to pass the invitation on to their daughters. After they had told the girls about the invitation, if the girls were interested, I would book a video call to tell them about the project and the activities in more detail, giving them a chance to have an informed decision about their participation in the project.

As for the live streamed concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*, besides advertisements to the general public, I got in contact with specific audience members, most of them musicians and artistic research practitioners. I explained them the participatory activities which would take place during the concert. Having this informed group was indeed helpful to encourage other audience members to engage with the participatory proposal. Among other actions, the participatory activities of the concert included walking around in the room while playing a sound with their mobile phones, as part of one of the pieces of the programme.

[\(Illustration: photo\)](#)

Chapter 3: Which methods?

Different types of online concerts may call for different methods of realisation, which may call for different methods of audience participation

The choice of the methods used for the audience participation will then depend whether the participatory proposal focuses on the *process* or on the *outcome*.

These are concepts distinguished by Astrid Breel¹, where the author traces a distinction between performances with a participatory *process* and performances with participatory *outcomes*:

- Participatory *process* proposals 'involve the participants in the creation of the work'.
- In proposals with participation in the *outcome*, the work is previously designed by the artist and the audience is involved in the realisation of the work.

The methods will also depend on the type of online concert, and on the target audience.

Some types of online concerts include:

- live-streamed concert with in-situ audience,
- live-streamed concert without in-situ audience,
- pre-recorded concert with scheduled premiere,
- pre-recorded concert to be watched "on demand",
- online concerts with live interactions,
- online concerts without live interactions, and so on.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

In the *music as an invitation* project, the first phase of the project had a participatory *process* proposal. While the general aim of the project was to create a collaborative online concert, the vision was to allow a space for the participants to feel free and to bring their own lived experiences and desires to the creative process. The chosen methodology, then, was Participatory Action Research, a methodology 'based on the principles of inclusion, valuing all voices and action-oriented interventions'.²

In this first phase of the project, the participants themselves took all the decisions regarding the creative process and elements. They decided not to have a set theme for the concert, instead to explore freely within creative strategies that they decided at each workshop. The online concert was then a consequence of this exploratory process.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes*

The second phase of the *music as an invitation* project asked for a different approach. After the first workshops of this phase, it was noticed that the free proposal did not suit this group of participants, therefore a methodology with more top-down direction was needed.

Here, then, the proposal assumed a participatory *outcome* characteristic: there was the goal to create material which would integrate a piece of music, which had been designed by the commissioned composer. In order to create that material to integrate the piece of music, the participants had to realise specific tasks, following a set of instructions designed by the composer.

When it came to the concert where *Hecate writes* was premiered - *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions* - the methods for audience participation followed the instructions of the

¹ BREEL A. (2015). Audience agency in participatory performance: a methodology for examining aesthetic experience. *Participations*, 12, p. 369

² <https://fass.open.ac.uk/research/projects/pasar> (Accessed on 29 April 2025).

participatory pieces which featured in the programme. Evidently, those participatory actions were to interfere or shape the performance of the pieces of the programme when performed by the in-situ audience. However, as an attitude of inclusion, the remote audience was also invited to perform the actions from wherever they were, what may have made an impact on their experiences as well.

Bonus case-study: *A festa da Clara*

In both phases of *music as an invitation*, the online audience was engaged prior to the performance, either by creating the online concert, or by creating material for a new piece of music to be performed in a concert.

Another possibility is for the remote audience to participate at the moment of the concert. A very common strategy of participation is the interaction via live chat and reactions in channels such as YouTube and Instagram. Although these kind of interactions are more commonly used to allow the remote audience to express their reactions, it can be interesting also to explore strategies where they can indeed interfere and help to shape the work.

For example, in the concert *A festa da Clara*, the audience participated by individually curating their programmes by exploring the resource of breakout rooms in the platform Zoom.

[\(Illustration promotional video A festa da Clara\)](#)

The audience entered the main session of the meeting, and from there they could choose to enter any of the four breakout rooms that were available simultaneously. In each breakout room there was a pre-recorded video of a theatre and piano performance, which was being played in loop. Each audience member could then stay as much as they wanted in each room. They would return to the main session, and follow up to any other room (or go back to the room where they were) according to their own wishes. There was one artist in charge of each breakout room, in order to start playing the video, manage any unforeseen troubles with the reproduction in loop, and to close the breakout room at the designated time. At a designated time, all the breakout rooms were closed, and there was a Q&A session in the main room with all the artists (four pianists and two actors) and audience members.

Although the audience interaction *A festa da Clara* did not change the content in itself, it did change in how it was realised in the experience of each spectator. No two people experienced the pieces in the same order, neither at the same length. Therefore, instead of having one programme for this concert, there were several 'programmes' which were individually curated by each audience member and simultaneously experienced.

Chapter 4: Preparing the infra-structure

The general design of the concert and its participatory category, as well the profile of the target audience and the chosen methods, are factors will determine which type of infra-structure will be needed for the realisation of the project.

When working with online projects, the first essential elements which the artist/ leader / facilitator will need are: access to reliable internet connection, controlling devices (computer, tablet or smartphone) and an appropriate physical place.

If the project involves participation through online workshops over a period of time, we will need access to video conference platforms. Also, subscription to paid services of the chosen platform may be needed to allow capacity of participants, the possibility of meetings with longer durations, and access to paid features such as automatic caption and cloud storage.

Equipment such as external microphones, speakers, headphones, and web-cameras may be desirable to ensure good quality of sound and image.

In projects that involve sharing of material, it can be helpful to think in advance about the online tools that can be used for storage and exchange, according to the requirements of the work and the possibilities of the participants. Popular cloud services such as Google Drive and Microsoft have been the favourite options for the participants of the *music as an invitation* project to exchange files during the creative processes. However, the project leader must certify if those services offer the appropriate level of security depending on the level of confidentiality and/or if the project involves handling of sensitive material.

Also, the development of the project may also require access to programmes such as design, video, and audio editing softwares.

The desirable features of the online concert and the way it will be delivered will also determine the infrastructure that will be needed.

For example, for both pre-recorded and live-streamed performances, popular streaming platforms such as YouTube or Vimeo may be sufficient if the aim is for the concert to be publicly available. But, will the concert is to be accessed by ticket/subscription holders only, there may be the need to look for specific platforms such as Idagio¹ or else to paid options on YouTube or Vimeo.

Also, the use of multiple cameras and multiple microphones can enrich the experience of the remote viewer, according to the aesthetic proposal of the project. In this case, additional technical support such camera operators, camera editors, and sound technicians will be essential.

If the concert is to be transmitted as an Instagram Live, we must ensure that the conditions for good quality of transmission via smartphone are met. This may include connection of smartphone to an appropriate microphone, proper camera framing and lighting, for example.

Additionally, one could want to consider the tools for live interaction, if that is desirable. Live chats are among the most common tool for live interaction. This feature must be activated beforehand in platforms such as YouTube, and we must consider who will be responding to the chat: if the artist themselves or if another designated person.

An aspect to be also considered, is about what new skills the artist /leader / facilitator may want to acquire in order to help the practical development of the project, and which tasks can be handled to other people - hired professionals or volunteer helpers.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

¹ <https://www.idagio.com/>

Since the *music as an invitation* project could benefit from the infrastructure of the university where it was hosted, the needed purchases mainly concerned digital subscriptions and softwares.

One of the first actions was to purchase a website hosting and domain plan for the project. The project website was going to work as an online hub, hosting the documentation and all relevant information of the project which could be shared publicly. The aim was for the website to have simple and efficient features, where I, the artist/researcher could be self-sufficient in terms of managing its content. In that respect, I decided to develop it myself, using the platform Wordpress, which is itself designed for self-publishing.

(Illustration: [website image with hyperlink](#)).

A friendly collaboration was arranged for the production of publicity material, so there was no need for purchase of design software neither hiring of a professional designer for this project.

For the online workshops where the online concert would be collaboratively developed, a Zoom subscription was purchased, so as to avoid time constraints for the meetings. Also, the paid subscription was necessary to have the option of automatic translation and caption, since the project wanted to include Portuguese speaker participants even if they were not fluent or comfortable with communication in English. The feature of automatic caption had then to be activated before the meeting, and an explanation of how to use it was given to the participants who wished to have this tool during the workshops.

As the creative process was taking place, it came the need to also acquire a video editing software, where the chosen one was Final Cut Pro. I had already knowledge of this programme, also I had a consultancy with the video technician of the university, so I could be in charge of the video editing that may needed during the development of the project, with the eventual help of some of the participants who may be interested in working on this part of the creative process as well.

During the online workshops, I made sure to be in a quiet room with reliable internet connection. Although I used good quality earphones during the meetings, in general there was no need for additional microphones neither extra cameras. I tried also to be in a room with access to a musical instrument in case the creative process called for musical interaction, which indeed happened once during the development of small group collaborations.

Initially, Microsoft Onedrive was the cloud storage programme used, since this was provided by the university. However, the participant themselves asked to use Google Drive, since they were more used to this programme. Also, some times the participants asked that some communications and exchange of files were done through WhatsApp or iMessage. This could be because those smartphone applications were more practical for them, or sometimes because they did not have access to computers.

A dedicated YouTube channel was set up for the project, which worked as a place to publish the works-in-progress, and to host the premiere of the online concert developed by the participants.

(Illustration: [image of YouTube channel with hyperlink](#))

Also, an Instagram profile was set for the project, aiming to enhance the experience of the participants through interaction on social media, and further reach of audiences for the project.

(Image of Instagram page?)

During the premiere, audience was encouraged to interact via Live chat, which was activated beforehand. I, as artist/research leader myself, was in charge of monitoring and responding the Live chat interactions.

Since the gathering of feedback was a crucial element in this project, a questionnaire was created using the platform Microsoft Forms (which was also provided by the university), which the participants could complete anonymously.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

Since the development of *Hecate writes* was part of the second phase of the project *music as an invitation*, most of the digital infrastructure have already been organised in the previous year. This infrastructure included: dedicated website, arrangement for production of publicity material, Zoom subscription, Final Cut Pro, project's Youtube channel and Instagram profile, project's Microsoft Onedrive and Google Drive folders for storage and sharing of files.

For the live streamed concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*, extensive infrastructure and technical support was needed.

For a better experience of the remote spectators, it was advisable to use a minimum of three cameras, where one camera gave a still overview to the concert, another camera gave a dynamic view spanning from the stage to the audience, and another camera had a closed focus on the details of the actions of the pianist.

The equipment needed for the live stream included:

- 2 cameras: 1 still, 1 moving
- SQ5 sound mixer
- ATEM mini Pro for live live stream editing

The technical team included:

- One sound engineer
- One assistant sound technician
- One live stream technician (who also was in charge of monitoring the live chat)
- One camera operator

It is important to verify in advance what are the requirements of the chosen platform to allow live streaming. For the concert *rsvp*, to this date, YouTube required phone verification and a waiting time of 24 hours before live streaming for the first time on an YouTube channel.

Chapter 5: Ethics

Participatory works, by definition, involve engagement with people. As a consequence, participatory works will nearly invariably require close attention to ethics. Indeed, as Claire Bishop points out, 'ethics is the ground zero of any collaborative art'.¹

As Ethics is a broad and complex topic, which can vary depending on the regulations of each place, this chapter has no intention to be comprehensive neither to work as legal advice. Rather, this chapter will just present some of the learnings about ethics, taken from the case studies. More detailed and official information about ethics in participatory works, as well as specific guidance, should be obtained from your local ethics and/or privacy protection regulatory bodies.

As a very first approach to understanding what ethics means and what it involves, we can think about Gundersen's concept which says that 'ethics is about how we relate to the world, and which impact we have on the world'.²

Therefore, participatory works must ensure that appropriate actions for respect, inclusion and justice are put in place.³ In practical terms, Williamon summarises the application of these ethical principles as:

- (1) Respect is put in practice by obtaining informed consent
- (2) Justice is put in practice by carrying out a fair selection of participants
- (3) Beneficence is put in practice by seeking not to harm and to maximise the benefits to the participants⁴

A cornerstone practice in the ethics of projects that involve humans is the requirement of 'prior, free, informed and ongoing consent of all those participating in research'.⁵ It is crucial that each participant understands the purpose of the project, what their participation involves, any potential benefits and risks, and that they have the freedom to withdraw their participation.

Usually, it is a requirement in projects involving humans that participants read information sheets and sign an informed consent form.

According to the Norwegian National Research Ethics Committees, 'the ethical consent should safeguard the participants' personal integrity and right to decide for themselves whether they want to participate'.⁶ Also, it is highlighted that the consent should be voluntary and without any kind of pressure.

¹ BISHOP, Claire. 2012. *Artificial Hells: Participatory Art and the Politics of Spectatorship*. London; New York: Verso Books. P. 218

² GUNDERSEN, J., et al. 2021. Map ethics! A method for identifying and addressing ethical dimensions of artistic projects. Part of Erasmus+ project Advancing Supervision for Artistic Research Doctorates. Available at <https://advancingsupervision.eu>

³ The three ethical principles that underlie the US Federal Policy for the Protection of Human Subjects, according to Williamon et. al., are: (1) respect for persons, (2) beneficence, and (3) justice. Ref.: *Performing Music Research: Methods in Music Education, Psychology, and Performance Science* by Aaron Williamon, Jane Ginsborg, et al.

⁴ WILLIAMON, A., Ginsborg, J., Perkins, R., & Waddell, G. 2021. *Performing music research: Methods in music education, psychology, and performance science*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198714545.001.0001>

⁵ CHEVALIER, Jacques M. And Buckles, Daniel J. (2021). *Handbook for Participatory Action Research, Planning and Evaluation*, SAS2 Dialogue, Ottawa. P. 23

⁶ <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en/guidelines/social-sciences-and-humanities/guidelines-for-research-ethics-in-the-social-sciences-and-the-humanities/>

Usually, consent should be obtained from people who are fully capable of responding for themselves. Generally, consent for the participation of children are obtained from their parents/guardians. In the case of participation of people with reduced or no ability to safeguard their own needs and interests, it is important to seek specific advice from the local regulatory bodies which are in charge of ethics and privacy protection of individuals.

Normally, consent forms should also include permission to recordings and for dissemination of the material produced in the participatory process. As reminded by Williamon et.al, 'transparency is important',⁷ therefore all the information about the project must be communicated clearly

Confidentiality and protection of privacy are usually a priority in projects that involve humans. However, an interesting point is raised by Chevalier, who observes that 'for some, recognition and 'being heard' may matter more than privacy and confidentiality',⁸ This in an interesting question, which, in our experience, can be discussed directly with the participants - would they prefer to be kept in anonymity so their privacy is protected, or is it more valuable for them to be acknowledged? Chevalier advises that 'respect to individuals must be shown through proper quoting, acknowledgements, co-authorship, or the granting of intellectual property rights'.⁹

Regarding online concerts, specifically, issues concerning ethics in the internet context may also emerge. Some challenges could emerge particularly in relation to data protection and the distinction between private and public.¹⁰ Specifically, it is important to keep in consideration when thinking about the ethics in online participatory projects, that communication via the Internet 'is stored, it is searchable, it can be copied, and the nature of the audience is often unclear'.¹¹

At the beginning of the *music as an invitation* project, it was stated that the aim of the participatory activities was to promote dialogues, collaboration, and a culture of compassion. Those principles were then the reference for the ethical standards put in practice during the development of the project.

Case study 1: project *music as an invitation* (year 1 and year 2 online creative processes)

The project *music as an invitation* was a research project, therefore it followed the guidelines of the ethics committee of the institution where it was inserted.

Firstly, the project was submitted for approval by the Research Ethics Committee at the University of Bergen. Also, because it involved the collection of personal data (for example, names and emails), it was submitted to the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research.

During the recruitment phase, I explained verbally, in introductory online meetings, the details of the project: the background to the research, the aims, the methods to be used, how their participation would happen, and the goals of the participatory process that they would be part of. Then, the potential participants received an information sheet with details in written about the

⁷ Performing Music Research: Methods in Music Education, Psychology, and Performance Science by Aaron Williamon, Jane Ginsborg, et al.

⁸ Chevalier, Jacques M. And Buckles, Daniel J. (2021). *Handbook for Participatory Action Research, Planning and Evaluation*, SAS2 Dialogue, Ottawa. P. 23

⁹ Chevalier, Jacques M. And Buckles, Daniel J. (2021). *Handbook for Participatory Action Research, Planning and Evaluation*, SAS2 Dialogue, Ottawa. P. 23

¹⁰ *A Guide to Internet Research Ethics*. The Norwegian National Research Ethics Committees. 2019. p.5. <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en/guidelines/social-sciences-and-humanities/a-guide-to-internet-research-ethics/>

¹¹ *A Guide to Internet Research Ethics*. The Norwegian National Research Ethics Committees. 2019. P. 5 <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en/guidelines/social-sciences-and-humanities/a-guide-to-internet-research-ethics/>

project, what their participation involved, clear statement that their participation was voluntary and they had the right to withdraw their consent at any time with no need for explanations, also details about how their personal data would be stored, their rights and who to contact if they had any questions or complaints about the project. A version of the information sheet was adapted to a teenage-friendly style (which included illustrations, for example) for the teenage girl participants.

Attached to the information sheet there was a consent form, to be signed by the participant, or by one of their parents/guardians in the case of participants under 18 years old.

(Insert image of consent form?)

Those documents were available in English and in Portuguese, but the participants (and the parents of parents/guardians of teenage participants) were informed that I could also arrange translations to other languages, if they so would feel more comfortable.

Also, in the online workshops, I would ask at the beginning of the meeting if all the participants would agree to have the session recorded.

Due to the characteristics of the participants of this project, the environment was naturally of respect, and I tried to make sure that everyone could feel included and have their voice heard.

The primary goal of the participatory process in the *music as an invitation* project was to foster contexts where the participants feel accepted, valued, and empowered. To this, my priority was to conduct the participatory process with social empathy, sensitivity and appropriate techniques of facilitation. For example, participants who were shier were kindly encouraged to participate in the discussion, yet they were respected in their individuality.

Case study 2: *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

The live streamed concert of the second year of research involved the sensitive issue of recording images of people - in photo, audio, and video.

To address this question, there were signs put in visible places in the venue informing:

This concert is being photographed and filmed for documentation, research, and promotional purposes. If you do not feel happy to be photographed or filmed, please let me, the photographer and/or one of the videographers know.

I announced this information verbally at the beginning of the concert as well. Also, I explained that, after the concert, audience feedback was going to be collected through audio recording. The recording of their feedback was going to be voluntary and anonymous, and would be used for research purposes only.

(Insert image - poster)

Chapter 6: Into the process

Once the project has been designed, the methods have been chosen, the target audience has been defined, the participants have been recruited and selected, and the materials are organised, it is time to bring the participants to the process of developing the project (the concert, or part of it, depending on the goal of each project).

For projects involving participation in advance to the concert, the scheduling of meetings and/or workshops can be a great challenge, which can be met from different styles / strategies. One style may be for the leader to set a date and time and inform it to the participants. Another style may be for the leader to inquire about the participants' availability and try to find a common time.

While the first option may have the advantage of simplifying the process for the leader and keeping the dynamic more objective, it may set a top-down tone to the project, also loose the engagement of some participants who could not attend on the set date and time. On the other hand, although the second style may set a more democratic tone from the start of the project, it may bring extra management difficulties specially when dealing with a larger group and presenting factors such as multiple time zones.

In either case, some elements to be taken account when scheduling meetings / workshops include:

- The characteristics of the target audience and their usual routine: for example, if there are school age participants, it is imperative to avoid school hours (unless the project is included in their school hours activities).
- Time zones, if the participants are joining from different places
- The timescale of the project, including feasibility of the tasks to be done by the participants in between meetings / workshops (if applicable).

In regards to the timescale of the project, it may be interesting to draw a timeline, where the participants can clearly visualise the steps, phases or milestones of the project. Depending on the chosen style of leadership and/or other characteristics of the project, this timeline can be either traced collaboratively with the participants, or can be drawn by the leader and communicated to the participants later on. In either situations, our experience has shown that it is helpful to always allow extra time for the completion of steps and/or milestones, and to beware of the need to be flexible at certain times.

Besides the infrastructure mentioned in the previous chapter, the preparation also includes the organisation of any other materials that may facilitate the unravelling of the meetings / workshops. This may include ice-break exercises, visual material for presentation of the project, activities, visual or sound examples for the development of some ideas,

It is then important for the leader / facilitator to prepare for the meeting / workshop. One aspect that may be interesting to consider, is the style of leadership and the tone for communication. Astrid Breel points out how essential the development of a relationship between artist and audience is, highlighting that

It is therefore necessary to consider the way the artists approach the audience, the way invitations are framed, and how the tasks build throughout the work.¹

A proposal of inclusion is generally understood as central to participatory works. Therefore, it is important for the artist / facilitator to develop skills of empathy and be attentive that the meeting / workshop has an inviting environment where the participants feel comfortable. The artist / facilitator need to be sensitive to differences in cultural and social backgrounds, and be attentive to the participants' different kinds of personality. For example, there may be situations where some participants are quieter and seem not be engaging in the discussions of the workshop. The artist / facilitator may need to be sensitive then to help them to engage actively, however in a way that they will not feel exposed.

¹ BREEL A. (2015). Audience agency in participatory performance: a methodology for examining aesthetic experience. *Participations*, 12, p. 379.

Another great challenge, specially when working with volunteers, is to keep the participants motivated. Here, our experience showed that the interpersonal relationships developed between artist and participants, as well as the development of an inclusive environment, are among the most powerful elements to keep the participants' motivation. Also, it is crucial to present and maintain inspiring and intriguing creative proposals, simultaneously to realistic expectations regarding the tasks for the participants. It can be helpful to maintain clear, warm and empathetic communication, as well as an ongoing accountability regarding the management of the project.

In projects that involve production of materials by the participants throughout a period of time, it is crucial to keep the communication, calendars, and files organised as the development of the project unravels. There are several methods and tools available for such organisation, including sharable cloud storage programmes, online calendars and forums. A well organised project is helpful not only for the artist / leader / facilitator herself, but for the participants as well. They can thus have confidence on the leadership, also have the possibility to also feel in control regarding their own participation in the project.

The management of the pace of the project is also very important, not only to ensure the timely development of the work, also to help in the motivation and enthusiasm of the participants. In our experience, when a project is developed over a long period, there are moments when there is more energy which reflects in a higher volume of communication, for example. This is balanced with periods of more quietness, which can be moments when some editing are done, for example. A crucial moment, however, is the anticipation for the delivery of the work which the participants have been involved. Here, the artist / leader / facilitator needs to develop skills to bring the participants together and build a positive atmosphere of expectation for the culmination of such collective work.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

In the *music as an invitation* project I first asked each participant, via email, their availabilities before scheduling each workshop. Although this dynamic demanded a great amount of administrative time, it helped to establish a democratic leadership style and a horizontal dynamic.

My aim was for the workshops to be spaces where conversations would flow naturally. Nevertheless, I would always have a set of questions prepared to stimulate the conversations. Since this group was very participative, usually the participants themselves would quickly volunteer to speak after I asked a question and would respond to each other, keeping the conversation up. However, sometimes I noticed that some participants had been quiet for a long time. I tried to gently encourage them to speak, by asking them some questions directly. I tried to keep an warm and informal tone. Sometimes some participants would ask my vision as the leader of the project, but I tried to encourage them to suggest ideas instead, positioning myself as a facilitator or even as a participant as well.

The experience was very welcoming, open and inclusive. I felt enough time was given for each of the participants to voice their opinion. The questions posed by the moderator were non judgmental and therefore I could express freely my opinion (it was equal either/or).²

We decided that the workshops were to have a monthly frequency. Due to the deadlines of the project regarding to the funding agency, I proposed a goal date for the finalisation of the collaboration and presentation of the online concert. I then drew a timeline and posted it on the projects website.

(Illustration: [timeline](#))

The participants were in five different time zones, and many of them were professionals who worked office hours. Therefore, the meetings usually happened on Saturday afternoons (in the European time zones), which was the time and day that would usually suit all the participants.

² Feedback from a participant, through anonymous questionnaire.

In between the workshops I made sure to send reminders to the participants via email. These reminders were helpful to keep the motivation of the group up, however I tried not to contact them too much so as not to have the opposite effect of becoming intrusive or inappropriate.

The gentle and inclusive tone of the project was also built from an attitude of understanding with potential delays and eventual absences. This was possible due to the freer nature of the creative proposal, and the emphasis on the process rather than on the final product.

As the date for the premiere was approaching, the project took a faster pace, with more meetings to work on the editing of the online concert video. The involvement of the participants in other tasks (video editing, poster) also helped to increase the energy in those days leading up to the concert.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

For the second year of the project music as an invitation, I initially sought to keep the democratic-horizontal style of leadership of the first year. Similarly to the first year, I firstly asked the availability of each participant in order to find common times to schedule the workshops. However, sometimes it was indeed not possible to find a common time. On those occasions I had individual meetings with participants who could not attend the workshop. However, for workshops where the participants were supposed to work together, it was imperative to find a day and time that would suit everyone.

For this group, which was made of teenage girls, the proposal of setting a space for conversations and free explorations did not seem to be flowing so easily. Then, a decision was made to change the focus, now with a direct objective to realise a piece already designed by a commissioned composer: *Hecate writes*, by Alwynne Pritchard.

Here, there were clear tasks to be done by the participants either during the workshops or in between meetings which usually happened every three weeks. This more condensed timescale was beneficial to keep the motivation of the girls up, besides the creatively inspiring characteristic of the project itself.

Although a more top-down style of leadership was needed with this group, I tried to keep to keep a warm tone and establish an environment of inclusion and understanding.

Since this was a group made of under-age participants, communication with the parents was essential. Firstly, the communication with parents was a requirement of the Ethics regulations of the project. This mediation was also helpful for the organisation of workshops, to keep the participants motivated and aware of the deadlines for the tasks. It also eventually gave me some insights about the girls' experience of the project which I could not get from them directly.

The work with this group of teenagers revealed the necessity to have sensitivity about generational differences, the importance of understanding about the demands of this age, and trust in their ability to rise to challenges. Sometimes, some of the participants indeed missed a deadline for the delivery of a certain task. In those occasions, it was helpful to have allowed extra time in the timescale. Also it was important to appreciate that this age group, nowadays, is usually under great pressure from school and other demands. Even so, all the participants showed much dedication in the accomplishment of their individual tasks, which were still delivered in time for the development of the next steps of the creative process.

The piece developed with the teenage girls - *Hecate writes* - was premiered in the live streamed concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*, which also featured participatory elements for the in-situ audience.

The participatory proposal of this concert did not require workshops in advance. Rather, they involved providing materials and instructions to the audience during the concert itself.

(Illustration: concert programme)

Firstly, I had told some audience members in advance about the participatory actions that they would be asked to do during the concert. Thus, these pre-informed people could lead the others by example, helping the artistic proposal to flow in a more organic way.

In order to suggest an inviting atmosphere, the room was set in a 'café-style', with chairs around small tables. Also, the door was open during the concert, and there was a sign saying that latecomers were invited to enter at any time. I prepared 'audience participation kits' - small paper bags with the material that the audience would need for the participatory actions - and placed them on the audience's chairs. For the remote audience, in the publicity of the concert there was a suggestion for the listeners to have with them the material needed for the participatory actions, in case they would like to experience them as well.

(Illustration: photo)

During the concert, I tried to keep a warm and informal tone in my communication with the audience, both in-situ and remote. I gave the instructions before each piece, and even joined the audience when the piece of music allowed me. The instructions were also written in the live chat before each piece by a person in charge of communicating with the remote audience during the live stream.

(Illustration: screenshot of live chat)

Although this concert had majorly positive feedback, both from the in-situ and the remote experience, the element of instructions is still a question to be developed. Firstly, since the communication was in English, this can compromise the reach of audiences who do not speak this language. Also, the verbal communications could sometimes break the flow of the concert as a whole. Additionally, how to find a balance of how much instruction to give - not too little that the specific proposal of the piece is not met, not too much so not to become didactic and cut off the creative input from the participants?

Summarising the steps of Into the process of developing a participatory online concert:

- Scheduling the first meeting
- Preparing for the meeting
- Finding a tone / style of leadership
- Creating an inviting environment / engaging your participants
- Keeping participants motivated - communication, accountability
- Keeping the materials organised - helpful for you and for your collaborators
- Warming up for the culmination - the delivery of the concert!

Chapter 7: Delivering

After so much collective dedication to the development of the concert, or of part of it, it is time for the culmination of the process: the presentation of the final product - the online concert.

Here, there are at least two possibilities when it comes to presenting an online concert:

- The presentation may be the live stream of a performance happening at the moment, or
- It may be the presentation of a pre-recorded material.

For pre-recorded material, a reasonably common practice is to set a premiere date. This can be felt as a gathering time as well, when all the participants come together to celebrate their collective achievement. In our experience, these moments of online premieres can bring emotions which resemble experiences of in-situ concerts, which involve the sense of anticipation and feelings of being part of a temporary community.¹

However, there may be situations when it will not be possible or not desirable to set the presentation of the online concert as an event. In that case, the online concert will be available on the chosen platform and will remain available for watching on demand.

Maybe it will be decided that the final product will have only a private viewing, just for the participants, or for the participants and a few guests. Or, maybe the concert will be available to the wide public. Or, there may be a situation where the concert will be premiered to a selected audience only (the participants, or the participants and a few guests), and will be available to the wide public later on.

Also, the technicalities of availability of the concert can vary: perhaps the concert premiere will be openly available on free access platforms such as YouTube or Vimeo. Or, it will be publicly available in social media platforms that require registration such as Instagram or Facebook. Or, maybe the concert will be accessed through a paid service such as Stage+² or a dedicated website such as the Royal Ballet and Opera Stream³. Also, perhaps the presentation will happen through a video-conference platform such as Zoom, where there the audience will have to have access to a link in order to join the event.

The decision about the aimed audience and the type of access for the presentation will depend on the characteristics and specifications of the project. Also, in projects like the *music as an invitation*, it is possible or even desirable to decide with the participants about to whom the online project will be available and how it can be accessed.

The decision about the aimed audience and the platform for the premiere of the online concert will make an impact on the platform to be used, on the date and time of the event, publicity tools and strategies, among other elements.

Regarding the date and time of the premiere, one option is to decide it in consultation with the participants. This option can be interesting to keep the democratic-horizontal style of leadership, if that is the approach of the project.

However, for a number of reasons, there are situations where may be more realistic for the leader to decide on a date and time and inform it to the participants. In that case, it may be interesting to notice elements such as different time zones, also if whether weekdays or weekends are more suitable so as the participants can watch it remotely.

¹ Georgina Born points out that 'music animates imagined communities, aggregating its listeners into virtual collectivities or publics based on musical and other identifications'. BORN, Georgina (ed). 2013 *Music, Sound and Space : Transformations of Public and Private Experience*, Cambridge University Press. P. 32

² <https://www.stage-plus.com/>

³ <https://www.rbo.org.uk/stream?tab=explore>

When presenting the concert, it may be also interesting to consider how the interaction with the remote audience will take place. This is an aspect that can make an impact on how the audience - both participants and other audience members will feel connected and part of what is happening⁴. In our experience featuring a welcoming message, either pre-recorded or spoken live, showed to be a helpful way to make the remote viewer feel included in the event, even though not present at the same space.

Also, several platforms offer the option of interaction via live chat, which can be an useful tool to engage with viewers specially during premiere of pre-recorded material. In situations of live streaming, an option for interaction can be verbal acknowledgement and responses to comments placed in the live chat. In those situations where the performer is the same person to be responding to the live chat, it is important to have the equipment to access the live chat (computers and/or smartphones) set in a way that will not disturb the performance itself. Also it is helpful to practice beforehand the alternation between music performance and verbal interaction, as if this dynamic were an artistic performance in itself.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

Following the horizontal dynamic that it was established in the creative process of the first year of the project *music as an invitation*, most of the decisions about the delivery of the collaborative online concert were taken collectively with the participants.

Due to the institutional requirements, there was indeed a period deadline for me to present the online concert, as the artistic product of the first year of project. In conversation with the participants, a date and time within that period was then decided.

The participants themselves had chosen to present the online concert as an YouTube premiere of a pre-recorded material which they had developed collaboratively. It was also unanimous that they would like that the premiere would be openly available to the wide public, as a moment to show their work to the world. To this, one of the participants volunteered to make a digital poster to be publicised through social media and emails by all participants.

(Illustration: poster)

The sense of anticipation was enhanced by the intensification of actions in the weeks leading up to the premiere, when we had more workshops to work together on the final editing of the concert. Also, I sent email reminders to the participants in the week of the premiere.

During the concert, we were all connected and interacting via live chat, what indeed brought a sense of collective experience. The interaction on the live chat also with other people who have not been involved in the creative process - in a sense they were *our* audience - also helped to create a sense of occasion among the participants.

(Image of screenshot with live chat)

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

For the delivery of the online concert of the second year of the *music as an invitation* project, a more top-down dynamic was needed. Considering how the second year of project unraveled, I took the decision that the piece *Hecate writes* - which had been developed with the teenage girl participants - would be premiered in a in-situ concert. This concert would be available for the participants to watch, as it was essential for the research to hear their feedback.

⁴ 'The feeling of always being connected to other people' (Auslander 2008: 111) is the core of the definition of 'liveness', which was the central topic of the investigation of the project *music as an invitation*.

However, the decision whether the concert would be live streamed or recorded and available afterwards was taken in conversation with the participants.

Since there were several factors to be taken in account - availability of the venue and technical support, and research deadlines - I then decided the date of the concert and communicated to the participants. Fortunately, all of them confirmed to be available to join the live stream on that date, and to participate in a last online meeting the following day to share feedback.

Aiming to build up a sense of 'being part' in the online viewers, I started the live stream from the moment when the in-situ audience was arriving at the venue. I thought then to evoke in the remote spectators the feelings of anticipation that emerge from the sounds, movements, and social interactions of the audience when occupying the performance room.

During the concert, since I could not access the live chat myself, I had help from the live stream technician to interact by posting welcoming and ending messages, also instructions for the participatory works, and responding eventual questions from the remote audience.

However, I made sure to acknowledge the online viewers in my verbal communication throughout the concert. This, included mentioning that some of the collaborators of *Hecate writes* were watching the concert remotely. Also, I aimed to encourage a continuous engagement of the online viewers by asking them to leave their feedback in the live chat and that I would read them later on.

[\(Image of live chat\)](#)

Summarising the steps of 'Delivering' an online participatory concert:

- What type of material: live or pre-recorded?
- What type of presentation: premiere event or on-demand watch?
- What type of audience: limited audience or wide public?
- What type of access: closed or open access?
- Setting date and time: building up anticipation
- Presenting the concert: interaction - making the remote viewers to feel close

Chapter 8: Documentation

Documentation is an essential part of the artistic practice, be it in traditional or in novel formats.

As highlighted in the Prazzle Performance Art Guide, 'documenting your performances is crucial because it not only preserves your work but also serves as an archive of your artistic journey'.¹

Documentation of online participatory concerts can be greatly helpful for assessment and learning from the experience. It is seen that

'Documentary evidence, whether it is in the form of written, audio, or visual data, can shed light on what people do, what they think, and how they present themselves and their experiences, beliefs, and feelings'.²

There are situations when the project purposely asks for non-documentation (for example, when the ephemeral is the centre of the proposal). Even in those cases, if the ephemeral proposal applies to the concert in itself only, it can be useful to document certain aspects of the creative process and/or the after thoughts.

In the area of online participatory projects, sometimes the documentation is a core part of the work itself. Sometimes, documentation is indeed inherent in the creative process.³

In online participatory concerts, usually we can organise at least three phases of documentation:

- Documentation of the process
- Documentation of the concert
- Documentation of the after-concert (feedback, reflective process, further impact)

The documentation of the process may involve archiving communication, which can be a helpful tool for reminders, for example. Also, in our experience, sometimes spontaneous comments would emerge in the emails and chats, which then became interesting material for reflection later on.

For the documentation of the process and of the after-concert actions, recordings of the workshops with participants can be valuable pieces of documentation. The documentation of workshops can involve video and/or audio recording, photographs, sketches, and written notes. Additionally, blog entries, questionnaires, and social media posts can be interesting tools to document the creative process, participants feedback, and impact of the project.

It is important however to ponder if the fact of being documented can inhibit some participants and prevent them to be spontaneous and engage fully in the creative and/or reflective process.

Regarding documentation of the concert, often, the video of a pre-recorded concert can be the documentation itself. On the other hand, with live streamed concerts, usually there is a choice of having the recording of the transmission as the documentation. Alternatively, some live stream productions could have the possibility of keeping the recordings of each source separately as the documentation of the concert (audio, individual cameras, etc).

Besides video and audio, programme notes are valuable pieces of documentation.

¹ <https://www.prazzleinc.com/editorial/how-to-document-your-performance-as-a-performing-artist>

² WILLIAMON, A., Ginsborg, J., Perkins, R., & Waddell, G. 2021. Performing music research: Methods in music education, psychology, and performance science. Oxford University Press. p. 109

³ NELSON, R., & Nelson, R. 2022. Practice as research in the arts (and beyond): principles, processes, contexts, achievements (Second edition.). Palgrave Macmillan. P. 82

Additionally, it could also be relevant to keep photo documentation of the concert. An interesting idea could be to keep screenshots of the moment of the concert, documenting the interactions and emotions that may have emerged at that moment. For live streamed concerts, the possibility of photo documentation of the event can be a helpful complement to the documentation of the project.

Specially when documenting through video, audio, and photographs where it is possible to recognise people, it is imperative to consider the ethics specifications of the project, which often require informed consent from participants and visible notices to the in-situ audience.

Due to its also academic research context, a Data Management Plan was required for the implementation of the *music as an invitation*, which included the strategies for documentation of the data generated by the project. Taking in consideration concerns about confidentiality, protection of privacy of participants, as well as practices of Open Science, this plan included different ways of storage for according to the different levels of sensitivity in the material. For example, data which contained personal information of the participants ought to be stored in a high security repository, while the performance videos that were intended to be watched by anyone could be stored in open access platforms.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

In this project, it was very helpful to keep a record of the communication with the participants, which happened via emails, WhatsApp texts, iMessage, and Instagram Direct Messages. Sometimes, these messages worked as reminders of dates and ideas. Also, sometimes some participants spontaneously shared some thoughts in those channels of communication which were helpful in the reflective process of the project.

The project also had a dedicated website⁴ which worked as a repository of the documentation through out the creative, delivery, and reflective processes. Also I wrote blog posts, which are part of the project's website, to keep track of reflective notes and other elements in the development of the project.

(Illustration: screenshot of blog page?)

With the consent from the participants, the online workshops were recorded in audio and video using the Zoom tool to record meetings. Also, I kept handwritten notes, which were practical for me to access specific topics later on, without the need to locate them inside the recordings.

The material produced by the participants during the creative process - short video and audio recordings - has a documentation nature in itself. I kept records of this material through publications on YouTube which were then embedded on the project's website, social media posts, also in physical and online storage devices.

Similarly, the online concert had a documentation nature in itself, since it was a compilation of the creative process. The online concert was published on YouTube, embedded on the project's website, and extra copies have been saved in dedicated storage units.

I then kept screenshots of live chat as documentation of the reactions during and right after the concert. The feedback meeting which happened with the participants through Zoom right after the concert was recorded in video, audio, and I kept my written notes as well.

Collaborative work have also the potential to create affective bond among the participants. Reflecting this interpersonal aspect of the project, the participants asked that we did a screenshot to document the faces of the group.

Although, when working with people, there are moments that inspire such warm gestures, one should make sure to respect and protect the privacy of individuals when recording faces: in the *music as an invitation year 1*, all the participants were adults, they asked themselves to be

⁴ <https://musicasaninvitation.com/>

photographed, and an extra-care was taken not to expose them on social media - this photo was shared privately with the participants and has been secured kept in password-protected storage units.

And additional piece of documentation was made from the anonymous online feedback form that the participants could fill out in the days following the concert, if they wished to.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

In order to protect the privacy of the teenage participants, most of the online workshops were not recorded. Indeed they had given me informed consent through reading and signing the information sheet, in advance to the workshops. However, I felt that it would be more sensitive not to record the meetings, also because they could have felt shy by been recorded. Only the workshop where there was hands-on collective development of creative material was recorded in video and audio, since this was a crucial step which I would need to revisit for my research. In all times, I kept my habit of taking written notes, which is my personal tool for evaluation and reflective processes.

The material produced by the participants - creative texts, audio and video recording - had a documentation nature in itself. However, differently from the previous phase of this project, I did not publish this documentation immediately, instead kept the files privately. This is because this material was going to be part of a commissioned piece of music, therefore I felt that it would be appropriate to protect the originality of the work.

When it came to the concert, the recording of the live stream itself on YouTube was taken as the video documentation. Photo documentation was also arranged, as complementation to the documentation.

The online meeting for feedback, which took place the day after the concert, was recorded in video and audio, also I did my usual written notes. Additionally, the participants were invited to fill out an anonymous online feedback form if they wanted to, and on their own time. Since some of them could not watch the concert at the moment of the live stream, the online form was a helpful strategy, so they could fill it out at any time after they watched the recording.

Also I maintained the dynamics of writing blog posts throughout the creative development, concert and reflective process, as a strategy to document the insights, feelings and learnings that were emerging during this phase of the project.

Since the *music as an invitation* was developed in a research context, all this documentation has been crucial as evidence of outcomes, and for written publications which usually follow up artistic works in academic environments.

However, even in non-academic contexts, appropriate documentation is an important element of an artistic practice. The process of looking back at documentation can reveals insights about the work which can be helpful in the development of new projects, and support production stages such as funding applications and promotion.

Chapter 9: The after-match

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the process of reflecting on the development and on the delivery of the concert can be a rich source of insights, which can be very helpful for the further development of one's practice.

These may include reflections on subjective aspects of the experience (for example, feelings, or creative inputs that may have emerged) and/or on practical issues of the production (for example, learning about recruitment strategies). Furthermore, reflections and analyses may be a required task for the elaboration of reports to host institutions and/or sponsors.

Some aspects of the reflective process may show similarities with qualitative analysis, which is 'a process of searching for meaning and understanding, seeking to illuminate participants' realities'.¹ In that respect, it requires the use of 'creativity, insight and knowledge to make sense of the complexity of the experiences and perceptions'.²

There are a variety of methods which can help in the reflective process, which can serve to different purposes, and be more appropriate to different affinities.

For example, the practice of free writing can be an interesting tool to capture impressions and feelings. Alternatively, the practice of voice recording can also be interesting, specially to capture spontaneity and inflections that cannot be expressed in written words.

When reflective processes such as free writing or voice recordings are done soon after the concert, emotions can be captured in the freshness of the moment. However, in some situations can be also interesting to take some distance and give some time before doing exercise of writing - which can then reveal aspects that have been engraved in the memory.

In the process of reflecting on the experience, it can also be helpful to analyse video, audio, photos, and other types of documentation. Also, looking back to one's own notes during the creative process can illuminate questions and bring up interesting insights.

Although it may be difficult to analyse a documentation material where we are deeply involved as an artist and/or producer, it is important not to ignore some undesirable elements which may have happened. On the contrary, an honest reflective process can engage with those 'less than optimal' elements and construct knowledge from their experience.

Some projects also involve collection of audience feedback. The analysis of such material can be a source of rich insights and a great learning opportunity.

Some simple initial questions can be helpful for one to start the reflective process, such as:

- What are the most immediate thoughts that come to mind, when thinking about the project?
- What was the most enjoyable element/ moment of the project?
- What was the least enjoyable element/ moment of the project?
- What was the initial aim of the project?
- How far has the project fulfilled its initial aims?
- What new insights came from this experience?

Some of these questions have been used in the feedback forms which were filled by the participants in the music as an invitation project. However, in our experience, they can be helpful tools to the help the reflective process of the artist / leader / facilitator and/or producer as well.

For some more in-depths analysis, Williamon et. al. suggest three types of analysis:

¹ WILLIAMON, A., Ginsborg, J., Perkins, R., & Waddell, G. 2021. Performing music research: Methods in music education, psychology, and performance science. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198714545.001.0001>

² idem

- Thematic analysis, which looks for key themes or patterns of shared meaning in qualitative data;
- Interpretative phenomenological analysis, which focuses on the lived experiences of individual participants in depth, looking into each participant's perspectives;
- Qualitative synthesis, which aims to offer a holistic view, by producing a narrative that tells the story of the experience, usually supported by a theoretical framework.

In some situations, specially when involving report writings to sponsors, there may be the need to analyse some practical and/or quantitative aspects as well, for example: reach (how many viewers and/or how many in-situ attendees), impact of the project (e.g. audience feedback, reviews, presence in local media, engagement on social media), by-products (videos, recordings, publishable texts, etc) and financial report.

The *music as an invitation* project was situated in a practice-based research context, therefore the analysing and report writing were mandatory steps in its development. Having the requirement to write an article about the the learnings from each year of research was then a helpful element, working then as a goal for the reflective process.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

As mentioned in the previous chapter, I kept the habit of logging my reflections as blog posts throughout the development of the first year of project. These entries turned out to be very helpful by the time I had to look back and gather what were the learnings from that phase of the research.

The analysis and reflection process also encompassed looking back on the documentation of the workshops - my personal notes and transcripts of conversations - and reading carefully the participants' responses to the feedback form.

As a first step, I retold how the creative process unfold, as if retracing the steps of the development of the project.

Subsequently, I went back then to the keywords which were set at the beginning of the project and aimed to identify excerpts of the participants' comments that related to those questions.

In this process of reading carefully the notes and feedback, I also identified some topics that emerged during the creative process - where some of those 'emerging learnings' were already noted down as blog posts in the website of the project.

Additionally, communications of the research in academic events, which I have presented throughout the first year of project, were useful material for me to look back and gather the topics that have been highlighted during the creative process.

Those reflections revealed learnings from two different starting points - from responses to questions set in advance, and from topics that emerged during the development of the project - which were then gathered in a section of 'Findings' in the academic article.

The text of the article turned out to become a book chapter, which will then refer to the multimedia documentation displayed as an exposition on Research Catalogue.

This phase of the project did not require a quantitative analysis. However, it was helpful for me to look back and document the number of participants and the countries where they were located, also for how many months the creative process was carried out and how many workshops took place. Since the main focus of the research was about the experience of the participants and my own, I did not find it relevant to keep account of how many views the online concert has been receiving.

However, the overview of the reach of participation of the project offered me valuable perspective, which has been helpful in the development of the second year of the project.

Besides the article / book chapter writing, the overview of the reach of the project and the findings from the first year of the project have been included in reports which had to be submitted to funding bodies.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

In the second year of the project *music as an invitation*, I carried on the practice of keeping track of my reflections through blog posts. Also I kept a kind of diary, where I logged more private reflections.

The reflective process of the second year of the project included looking back at those blog and diary entries, also to the participants' feedback which they shared through conversations and online feedback form. Additionally, listening to the feedback collected right after the concert offered some insights about the experience of the participatory experience of the in-situ audience/ participants.

In this second year of project I considered that it would be relevant to highlight the reflective process regarding my experience of the participatory processes as an artist. To this, the diary entries have been an essential source of information.

As part of the development of research within an artistic context, I have been exploring alternative ways to elaborate the article of this second year of project. I have been exploring compilation of small formats including short audio and/or video and text slides in the style of social media carousel.

(Embed <https://www.canva.com/design/DAGpziGTPeE/rRSBBanCEV5rGzMYvBEGjA/view>)

These small form publications aim to resonate the material that has been explored in the creative process - short videos made by the participants - and the social media context which relates closely to teenage girls' worlds. Also, the experiment with alternative formats aim to communicate, in an embodied way, the very 'smartphone-based' dynamic that the development of this turned out to be for me in this period of my life (reference to "Notes on motherhood")

The end of the second year coincides with the finalisation of the research project, which brings the requirement of elaboration and submission of reports to the funding agencies. Helpful strategies to elaborate those reports include: looking back at the initial proposal of the project, particularly the sections about the expected outcomes, and reflect about which results were obtained - both anticipated and unanticipated ones. For this type of project, there is no requirement of focus on quantitative analysis, although it will be interesting to include brief information about the number of participants and of countries involved in the participatory processes. The centre of attention for reflection, which will inform the project report, consists in analysing and summarising the new understandings that were gained from the development of this project, and which new insights the project brings to the fields of participatory arts and music performance.

Chapter 10: Taking it further - dissemination

Usually, to increase the reach of in-person concerts, one may do several performances of the programme and may tour the concert.

However, in the case of participatory online concerts, there is not really the possibility of touring.

How can we then take an online concert further?

There are some projects which feature a series of live stream concerts - a practice that was particularly wide spread during the coronavirus pandemic, specially through the feature of Instagram Live. However, recurrent live streaming performances of one specific programme are less-known, in our experience.

As for recorded concerts - either being the documentation of a live stream or a pre-recorded concert all-together - repetition is more feasible because the material can be made available to watch on demand. Such access can take place either freely as in platforms such as YouTube or Instagram, or via subscriptions to paid services such as the Berliner Philharmoniker Digital Concert Hall.¹

In the case of on demand recorded concerts, there is the potential to attract the attention of new or recurrent spectators in a type of passive way, just by the concert being available online. However, this potential can be increased by some more active strategies. For example, in our experience, engagement through social media has been a good strategy to call the attention of online audiences. Also, reviews in specialised magazines and blogs can help to bring visibility to the project.

If the concert is inserted in a research context, there are means of dissemination such as communications at conferences and publication of journal articles.² Similarly, lectures and workshops can be good opportunities to amplify visibility of the concert among academic and non-academic audiences.

Additionally, there is the possibility to submit the video of the online concert to film festivals and competitions. To this, one can apply to festivals and competitions that are focused on music, or general events which have a 'music video' category or similar. Also, we can look for thematic events that are related to the topic of the concert, for example: film festivals with a gender thematic, or competitions that are aimed to practitioners from certain geographical locations, and so on.

Depending on the requirements of the call for submissions of the desired festival or competition, the online concert can be submitted either in its original form or in an edited version. Incidentally, the possibility of producing an edited version of the online concert for further dissemination can be a stimulating opportunity for further creative development of the work.

However, it may be interesting to consider whether there might emerge questions relating to ethics and copyright concerning the participants when disseminating a participatory/collaborative work.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

The main strategy for dissemination of the online concert of the first year of the project *music as an invitation* was indeed posts on social media.

¹ <https://www.digitalconcerthall.com/en>

² see Williamon et. al. chapter on Communication and dissemination of research projects in music. In WILLIAMON, A., Ginsborg, J., Perkins, R., & Waddell, G. 2021. Performing music research: Methods in music education, psychology, and performance science. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198714545.001.0001>

Following the online premiere, I posted about it on the projects' and my personal social media pages, pointing out to the YouTube link where the recording could be accessed. Also, the concert was embedded on the project's website.

Since this online concert was part of a research project, conference presentations helped to communicate it to my academic peers. Similarly, I have shared the concert in online lectures to students and teachers of music programmes in High Education institutions.

Additionally, there are plans to submit this online concert to film festivals in order to further amplify its reach.

The actions for dissemination, besides being part of the research process, have also been opportunities where learnings keep emerging each time when the online is shown, revealing insights, provoking reflections and bringing up ideas for new projects.

Case study 2: *Hecate writes / rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

Since the recording of the live stream of the *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions* concert has remained available on YouTube, the strategies to bring attention to it include: sending the link to specific people via email, sharing about it on social media, and embedding it on the project's website.

Similarly to the year 1 concert, communications in conferences and in lectures have also been increasing the reach of the year 2 concert among audiences in research and educational environments.

Due to being a recording of a live stream concert, this concert does not appear, to me, as suitable to be submitted to film festivals and competitions.

However, the participatory piece which was central to this concert - *Hecate writes* - has indeed received recurrent performances since its premiere in the live streamed concert.

These recurrent performances of *Hecate writes* have been opportunities for me to become more and more intimate with the piece. Also, the varied feedback coming from diverse audiences has been offering varied perspectives and insights to reflect upon.

Thus, on one hand, the dissemination of the recording of the live stream has been an interesting tool to show my research and interests, and to build opportunities for further performances. On the other hand, recurrent performances of the key participatory piece - *Hecate writes* - have been opportunities to amplify the impact of the idea behind the online concert: processes of participation and collaboration in online contexts, and empowerment of the voices of teenage girls through a online collaborative music project.

Conclusion

The advances of digital technologies have opened up new possibilities for music performance. Through the internet, our performances can reach audiences beyond geographical barriers. Not confined to an specific time and place, individual listeners can experience concerts at the time of their convenience, from wherever they are.

However, with those possibilities, online concerts also bring challenges regarding one of the most precious aspect of live music: its ability to bring people together.

How can we feel 'being part' of a music experience which we are watching remotely, many times with no interaction with the performers neither other audience members?

In the experience of the *music as an invitation* project, explorations of participatory ideas for the audience can greatly help to build this bridge in the digital context.

As a participant of the *music as an invitation* project said:

I'm grateful to have met inspiring people during this process of creating music together. Even though each of us joined this process almost from another end of the world, I felt close and connected to other participants while exploring curiously together what music means to us.

For me, as a performing musician, the experiences of developing participatory projects have brought challenges, also new and gratifying perspectives for my practice.

Among the challenges, there was the stepping out of the usual 'introvert pianist character' and sending out invitation. There was also the opening of 'my' space of creativity to other people, and trying to build honest and meaningful interaction despite the layers of technology and physical distance among ourselves.

For months, instead of the usual intense dedication to piano practice, most of my work consisted on engaging with people and managing the many practical aspects of the participatory process. I could not help the rise of some doubts in my head such as:

'where is the artist' in this new collaborative context?

Then, I could realised that, instead of loosing the 'artist-I', she was actually gaining new horizons. It was as if the 'I' was amplifying to the point of becoming 'we', and this process was infused with affection and liveliness.

'We' is the result of an 'I' that opened up (that opened up to what she is not), that expanded, placed herself outside, expanded herself.¹

As the composer Alwynne Pritchard has commented that *Hecate Writes* 'is in essence a framework for the girls to be free to explore their creativity. In a sense, a space for them to be', I could now also see my role as a performer under a new light: as to offer frameworks fro music experience to happen.

As White delineates, 'people who invite participation are making art when they do so.'²

¹ MACÉ, Marielle, Isadora Bonfim Nuto, and Marcelo Jacques de Moraes. 2023. *Nossas Cabanas : Lugares de Luta, Ideias Para a Vida Em Comum*. Rio de Janeiro: Bazar Do Tempo.

² WHITE, Gareth. 2013. *Audience Participation in Theatre: Aesthetics of the Invitation*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

The practices of audience participation temporarily re-shape our social being, (...) and perhaps, on occasion, allow us to perceive ourselves anew.³

Also, the online collaborative process gave me the opportunity to engage in rich dialogues with women from different locations and life contexts, and build relationships throughout the collaborative process - what would not have the possibility to happen if we were in a traditional set up. Resonating with the experience of one of the participants:

For me, the best part of this project was to meet women from many countries around the world and be connected with them through music (participant in the *music as an invitation* project)

The experience of these participatory online concerts revealed the diffusion of single authorship into collaborative activities. And, more than offering singular artistic experiences, participatory art indeed works towards constructive social change.⁴

This volume was then written with the aim to be useful an useful practical tool to other artists and producers who are interested in exploring participatory online concerts.

In this book I shared the step-by-step experience of putting together the participatory online music performances of the *music as an invitation* project. The idea of this volume is be to an exchange of learnings from a very specific project, with modest infrastructure and small-scale audience reach which, nevertheless, made a lasting positive impact on the participants - myself included.

³ WHITE, Gareth. 2013. Audience Participation in Theatre: Aesthetics of the Invitation. London: Palgrave Macmillan. P. 206

⁴ BISHOP, Claire. 2012. Artificial Hells: Participatory Art and the Politics of Spectatorship. London; New York: Verso Books. P. 16

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